

PROPOSAL SUMMARY

Here we propose to develop Open Science training modules for artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) in space biosciences. We will design modules in the *OpenCore* style and format, in 2.5 hour interactive learning experiences to be taught in the mornings during a week-long meeting. Each week-long training course will cover a different topic, including fundamentals of AI/ML and space bioscience data, ethics and best practices for AI/ML and Open Science, and use cases which train students in specific algorithms to solve real-world problems using cloud-based NASA data.

SCIENTIFIC / TECHNICAL / MANAGEMENT PROPOSAL DESCRIPTION

Relevance to NASA Open-Source Science Initiative

Here we propose to develop Open Science training modules for artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) in space biosciences using cloud-based datasets from the NASA Open Science Data Repositories. The proposed efforts are in direct alignment with the NASA Science Mission Directorate's (SMD) Strategy for Data Management and Computing for Groundbreaking Science 2019-2024 Recommendation 10 "Explore AI/ML capabilities" and Recommendation 11 "Incentivize and educate the community on AI/ML".

The proposed work is also in alignment with the NASA SMD's Science Plan Science 2020-2024: A Vision for Scientific Excellence Strategy 1.3 "Advance discovery in emerging fields by identifying and exploiting cross-disciplinary opportunities between traditional science disciplines". The proposed training programs combine traditional space biology with fundamental AI/ML skills, to explore opportunities at this cross-disciplinary intersection.

Finally, the proposed work is in direct alignment with the NASA 2022 Strategic Plan Strategic Objective 1.3 "Ensure NASA's science data are accessible to all and produce practical benefits to society". The proposed training programs will directly utilize NASA science data from the Open Science Data Repositories and will provide training so that more people are positioned to generate knowledge gain from NASA data.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, and Open Science in Biology

Artificial intelligence (AI) is based on machine learning (ML) methodology, which trains a mathematical model on a set of training samples, in order to make predictions on previously unseen samples[1]. This powerful methodology has gained significant traction in the biological and biomedical research fields in the last two decades. Due to its capability for identifying complex relationships and patterns, AI/ML methodology is particularly well suited to recognize and predict biological patterns from high-dimensional next-generation sequencing data (e.g. whole genome sequencing, transcriptomic sequencing), as well as from biological or medical imaging data (e.g. microscopy, computed tomography, ultrasound, magnetic resonance imaging, radiography)[2,3]. With the sequencing revolution of the last decade and the explosion in high-dimensional sequencing data, AI/ML methods have become increasingly useful research tools for detecting patterns and networks within genomic data[4].

Indeed, current AI/ML toolkits enable scientists and physicians to accurately predict fundamental biological properties such as protein structure[5] and microbial species[6], or applied clinical outcomes such as time to disease onset[7], disease stage[8], specific diagnosis[9], overall disease survival[10], and drug response[11].

This proven success of AI/ML in biomedical sciences has been followed by a surge in overall interest and investment from academia, industry, and governmental agencies. The global computational biology market is projected to reach \$14.7 billion by 2028, in large part due to the demand for ML-based data analytics[12]. AI/ML expertise is now a desired attribute for many biomedical data analysis careers, and a search for "machine learning and biology" on Coursera returns nearly two dozen different possible certificates combining these domains. It is now possible for any interested person to train a predictive model with an open-source dataset and a few lines of code, leveraging public code libraries such as Python's *tensorflow*, *pytorch*, and *scikit-learn*.

However, there are many key considerations for properly training, validating, and testing a machine learning model in biological research or clinical application. A training dataset must be large and diverse enough to represent all aspects of the feature space, so that a trained model will be able to recognize patterns in previously unseen data. A small or unrepresentative dataset will generate an "overfit" model, which performs well on training data but cannot make fully accurate predictions when presented with new data. In the biomedical research field, many well-

trained AI/ML models have relied on re-using public data from large data repositories such as the Gene Expression Omnibus, the Sequencing Read Archive, or the Genomic Data Commons. These data repositories, together with the movement towards Open Science principles in biological research[13], has made it possible to assemble large training datasets with hundreds or thousands of data points.

Nevertheless, experience and skill are needed to properly design and train a predictive model. A poorly trained model may pick up intrinsic bias from the training data and make incorrect or even dangerous predictions. For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic, clinical data was generously shared between research groups in an effort to quickly characterize the viral disease. Even with the positive culture of Open Science and data sharing, inexperienced researchers working quickly without proper checks produced models that performed poorly outside of the immediate training dataset. A comprehensive and systematic review of AI/ML models generated with COVID-19 data found that 90% of models (545 out of 606) had a high risk of bias due mainly to "inadequate sample sizes" and "inappropriate or incomplete evaluation of model performance"[14].

Taken together, lessons learned from biological AI/ML research indicate that Open Science principles such as data sharing and open-source code must go hand-in-hand with publicly available, high-quality training curricula in best practices, with modules centered on real-life scientific use cases and data so future AI/ML practitioners gain experience on real problems.
Biological and Physical Sciences Priorities: Machine Learning Opportunities

The NASA SMD Strategy for Data Management and Computing for Groundbreaking Science 2019-2024 recommended exploring NASA AI/ML capabilities for scientific knowledge gain, and educating and incentivizing AI/ML adoption within NASA and the scientific community[15]. In keeping with these recommendations, there are several recent AI/ML developments which address the priorities of NASA Biological and Physical Sciences Division (BPS), including studying the effect of spaceflight on living and physical systems. A knowledge graph connecting over 40 biomedical databases was used to identify symptoms of terrestrial diseases connected with gene expression changes in spaceflown mice[16]. Consecutive teams in a space-focused AI/ML sprint challenge developed a causal inference machine learning ensemble, identified predicted causal gene expression changes in radiation-exposed blood samples from mice and humans, and implemented federated learning capabilities to train causal models on physically separated datasets, such as space- and Earth-bound data[17,18]. AI/ML methods have been used to predict radiation exposure or cognitive impairment in rodent models[19,20]. AI/ML-based network modeling has been used to predict spaceflight-relevant changes in vascular patterning in the eye for diabetic retinopathy[21], the intestine for inflammation changes[22], and *Drosophila* wing spaceflight adaptations[23]. AI/ML approaches have also been used to characterize antimicrobial resistance genes in microbial data from the International Space Station[24].

These previous efforts point the way for tremendous future potential for AI/ML and space biosciences research. The 2021 NASA Artificial Intelligence and Modeling for Space Biology workshop identified several key focus areas to advance space biosciences with AI/ML in the next decade, including leveraging AI/ML algorithms to predict effects of spaceflight stressors on living systems, using AI/ML to develop astronaut health monitoring systems, and developing new algorithms to address specific problems in space biosciences[25,26]. The National Academies call for the Biological and Physical Sciences Decadal Survey received several white papers stressing the importance of investing in AI/ML capabilities for widespread space-relevant applications, including health monitoring and space medicine[27–29], *in-situ* experimentation and analysis[28], materials research[30], new algorithm development[31], space plant production, monitoring, and analysis[32–34], and bioregenerative life support systems for space travel[35].

Cloud-based Biological and Physical Sciences Benchmark Datasets

The NASA Open Science Data Repositories (OSDR), GeneLab[36,37] and the Ames Life Sciences Data Archive (ALSDA)[38], publish raw and processed spaceflight and spaceflight-relevant biological experimental datasets. GeneLab hosts 'omics data (transcriptomics, genomics, proteomics, metabolomics) while ALSDA hosts phenotypic, bioimaging, video, behavioral, and other non-omics life sciences space data. These cloud-based data are available at the public repository: <https://osdr.nasa.gov/bio/> or by using the API: <https://visualization.genelab.nasa.gov/GLOpenAPI/>

These data are being developed into benchmark training datasets for training AI/ML models to find patterns of spaceflight effects in all biological data types. We have obtained through private communication that NASA SMD called for benchmark training datasets from each NASA Division in 2022. These datasets will contain the most common data types from each domain, containing representative samples and labels, to be used for sprints, challenges, or training courses. The Biological and Physical Sciences Division has developed 2 benchmark training datasets based on space biological data from the OSDR, representing 2 of the most common space biological data types. These datasets will be available on the cloud through Amazon Web Services (AWS) Open Data Registry by the end of 2022. Table 1 summarizes these datasets.

Dataset	Description	n samples	Labels	Cloud-based
<i>BPS RNA Sequencing</i>	Gene expression data from spaceflown mouse liver, augmented by generative adversarial network.	6,263	Condition (spaceflight/ground), sex, age, mouse strain, sequencing library preparation method	YES
<i>BPS Microscopy</i>	Fluorescent microscopy images of simulated space radiation treated mouse immune cell nuclei, stained for <i>53BP1</i> , a marker of DNA damage.	93,488	Number of DNA damage foci per nucleus (<i>nfoci</i>), type of radiation exposure (X-ray or Fe particle)	YES

Table 1. Cloud-based benchmark training datasets from NASA Biological and Physical Sciences Division.

Here we propose to develop ScienceCore curricula for training in AI/ML, using the BPS benchmark datasets as real-life scientific use cases, both to attract participants through engaging problems, and to train participants using real problems and data.

ScienceCore Modules: Training in Machine Learning for Space Biological Use Cases

Topic 1: Fundamentals of Machine Learning and Space Biosciences Domain

This Topic is designed to give novice students an introduction to AI/ML principles, training and validating a model, and the various popular algorithm types, all in the context of space biosciences and how AI/ML can solve key problems in space biological research. When possible, students with limited AI/ML experience may opt-in to taking this Topic prior to the use-case topics (3 and 4). Students taking this Topic are expected to have basic, but not advanced knowledge of Python.

At the end of this Topic, students will have a fundamental understanding of the differences between training an AI/ML and employing a traditional statistical analysis approach. They will have experience coding in Python in a Jupyter notebook, will understand the differences between supervised, unsupervised, classification, and regression algorithms, be familiar with the most common AI/ML approaches, and know how to design a typical AI/ML exploratory data analysis (EDA). They will understand the scientific goals of the space biology research field, understand which open research questions AI/ML is best suited to address, be able to access cloud-based

space biology open science data from the NASA OSDR, and will have trained a model on an OSDR dataset.

Below we summarize the proposed 5 modules within Topic 1. Each module will consist of a lecture, a hands-on training portion using Jupyter notebook, and a quiz at the end.

Module 1: AI/ML Principles

- Learning Objectives:
 1. Understand AI/ML vs statistics[39]
 2. Supervised vs. unsupervised
 3. Classification vs. regression
 4. How to use a Jupyter notebook
 5. Python libraries for AI/ML
- Lecture (45 minutes) – Mathematical Principles of AI/ML
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour): Jupyter notebook:
 - Jupyter notebook tutorial
 - Tutorial and examples of popular Python libraries for AI/ML
- Quiz (15 minutes): Given a description of a scientific problem, explain whether supervised/unsupervised, classification or regression approach is appropriate.

Module 2: AI/ML and Space Biology

- Learning Objectives:
 1. Space biology research goals[40]
 2. How to access open science space biology data (OSDR)
 3. How AI/ML can solve space biology problems[26,28,31]
- Lecture (45 minutes) – Overview of the Application of AI/ML for Space Biology Research
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour): Jupyter notebook: Edit and run existing code to:
 - Download OSDR space biology dataset
 - Perform preliminary EDA for AI/ML
- Quiz (15 minutes): Be able to describe the goals of space biology, and how to design an EDA prior to AI/ML analysis.

Module 3: Algorithm Selection (part 1)

- Learning Objectives:
 1. Know common classification algorithms (decision tree, k-nearest neighbor, logistic regression, support vector machine) and when to use them[41]
- Lecture (45 minutes) – Overview of Classification Algorithms
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour): Jupyter notebook: Edit and run existing code to:
 - Practice coding each algorithm using a small dataset
- Quiz (15 minutes): Given descriptions of scientific problems, choose and justify a classification algorithm for each.

Module 4: Algorithm Selection (part 2)

- Learning Objectives:
 1. Linear and non linear regression
 2. Neural networks (NN)[42]
 3. Causal inference algorithms[17,43]
 4. When to use each algorithm type
- Lecture (45 minutes) – Overview of Regression, NN, and Causality
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour): Jupyter notebook: Edit and run existing code to:
 - Practice coding each algorithm using a small dataset
- Quiz (15 minutes): Given descriptions of scientific problems, choose and justify a classification algorithm for each.

Module 5: Training a Model

- Learning Objectives:
 1. Data splits
 2. Selecting an appropriate algorithm
 3. Model training and validation
 4. Scientific interpretation
- Lecture (45 minutes) – Practical Implementation: Training a Model
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour): Jupyter notebook: Edit and run existing code to:
 - Download OSDR space biology dataset and perform appropriate data splits
 - Select, train and validate a model
- Quiz (15 minutes): No quiz, discuss scientific interpretation of trained model outputs.

Topic 2: Open Science, Artificial Intelligence, and Ethical Best Practices for Data Sharing and Analysis

This Topic is designed to give participants a fundamental understanding of AI/ML ethical best practices, including the importance of identifying and correcting bias in training data, appropriately validating the performance of a model, identifying and correcting overfitting to the training data, and employing explainable AI techniques to increase transparency and trust. These themes are further developed through a discussion of the importance of open science and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reproducible) data structure and data sharing for biological research in general, and space biological research in particular. Students will discuss hypothetical case studies to identify and solve issues of AI ethics, transparency, data sharing, data accessibility and fairness.

Below we summarize the proposed 5 modules within Topic 2. Each module will consist of a lecture, a hands-on training portion using either Jupyter notebook for coding or Google Jamboard for interactive discussion, and a quiz at the end.

Module 1: Ethics and Bias in Scientific AI

- Learning Objectives:
 1. How to identify and solve bias in scientific training data
 2. Best practices for ethical data science and AI/ML in science[44]
- Lecture (45 minutes) – Bias and Best Practices in Scientific AI/ML
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour)
 - Discussion: Case Study: Gender disparity in Astronaut cohort[50]
- Quiz (15 minutes): Given a case study, identify sources of bias and solutions.

Module 2: Explainable AI (xAI)

- Learning Objectives:
 1. What is xAI vs. "black box" algorithms[45]
 2. Abilities and limitations of xAI
- Lecture (45 minutes) – Principles and Examples of xAI
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour): Jupyter notebook: Edit and run existing code to:
 - Given a pretrained model, examine how the scientific interpretation changes with and without xAI
- Quiz (15 minutes): Given the outputs of a model, explain what features a useful xAI implementation would identify.

Module 3: Open Science Principles for AI

- Learning Objectives:
 1. What are the principles of Open Science[13]
 2. How does this impact scientific AI practitioners (open data, open code, reproducibility, transparency)
 3. NASA space biology Open Science Data Repositories
- Lecture (45 minutes) – Open Science: Principles and Practice

- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour)
 - Discussion: Case Study: compare historical AI predictions with closed and open data
- Quiz (15 minutes): Reproduce Open Science principles and explain their applicability to scientific AI.

Module 4: FAIR Data Sharing

- Learning Objectives:
 1. What are the FAIR data principles[46]
 2. How does this impact scientific AI practitioners
- Lecture (45 minutes) – FAIR Data and AI/ML
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour): Jupyter notebook: Edit and run existing code to:
 - Download datasets for AI/ML model training from FAIR and non-FAIR databases
- Quiz (15 minutes): Reproduce FAIR principles and explain their applicability to AI.

Module 5: Reproducibility

- Learning Objectives:
 1. Reproducibility in experimental science vs. data science
 2. How to ensure reproducibility in AI/ML model outputs[47,48]
 3. Current reproducibility crisis in science[49]
- Lecture (45 minutes) – Reproducibility in Scientific AI/ML
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour)
 - GitHub Tutorial: best-practices in publishing code, data and methods
- Quiz (15 minutes): Given a scientific workflow, identify items to publish for reproducibility.

Topic 3: Using AI/ML Classification to Identify Gene Networks Affected By Space Exposure in Mouse Liver

This Topic will focus on a real scientific use case using the BPS RNA Sequencing cloud-based benchmark training dataset. This dataset contains thousands of samples (real and synthetic) from space-flown and ground control rodent livers. Each liver sample has been processed for RNA sequencing, resulting in numerical measurements for the expression of 25,000 genes.

Gene expression data is extremely valuable in biological research because it provides a readout of gene activity in the tissue at the time of sampling. Changes in gene expression during an experimental treatment or condition (such as spaceflight exposure) can indicate biological mechanisms that are most affected by the condition. This provides researchers with a better understanding of the biological effects of spaceflight, and potential therapeutic targets for countermeasure development.

The liver gene expression benchmark dataset is particularly valuable because we know that spaceflight negatively impacts liver function[51–53], but we do not yet know why, which gene networks are involved, or how to mitigate this impact. Thus, students working through an AI/ML case study with this dataset will be focusing on a real and unsolved problem in space biology and astronaut health.

Our case study for this dataset will include performing an EDA, comparing the performance of 3 different classifiers (random forest, support vector machine, and invariant risk minimization), selecting an appropriate classifier, training the classifier to distinguish between spaceflight and ground control samples, identifying the informative features (genes) from the classification, and characterizing the functional relevance of these genes through gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA)[54] and biomedical knowledge graph analysis to relate rodent features to human clinical manifestations, and leveraging open source biomedical knowledge graphs with browser user interfaces: SPOKE (spoke.ucsf.edu)[55], and if time permits,

CROssBAR (crossbar.kansil.org)[56]. Students will be encouraged to discuss and engage with additional ideas for analyzing this dataset outside of this course.

Students will be expected to have basic, but not advanced understanding of Python and AI/ML classification (taking Topic 1 first is recommended).

Below we summarize the proposed 5 modules within Topic 3. Each module will consist of a lecture, a hands-on training portion using either Jupyter notebook for coding or a browser-based activity for interactive discussion, and a quiz at the end.

Module 1: EDA

- Learning Objectives:
 1. How to use clustering techniques and feature analysis to better understand a new numerical dataset prior to model training
- Lecture (45 minutes) – Best Practices for EDA for Numerical Data
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour): Jupyter notebook: Edit and run existing code to:
 - Use cloud tools to access the BPS RNA Sequencing benchmark training dataset from AWS Open Data Registry
 - Perform an EDA on the data
- Quiz (15 minutes): Given outputs of a hypothetical EDA, identify any interesting or concerning results.

Module 2: Comparing Classifier Performance

- Learning Objectives:
 1. How to use validation metrics (error, loss) to compare the performance and outputs of multiple classifiers: random forest (RF), support vector machine (SVM), and invariant risk minimization (IRM)
- Lecture (45 minutes) – Classifier Validation and Performance Metrics
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour): Jupyter notebook: Edit and run existing code to:
 - Create data splits
 - Train RF, SVM, IRM to distinguish spaceflight and ground samples
 - Compare validation outputs and performance and identify best method
- Quiz (15 minutes): Identify key validation metrics for AI/ML performance comparisons.

Module 3: Training a Classifier

- Learning Objectives:
 1. How to train a classifier on numerical data
 2. How to derive the most important features for downstream analysis
- Lecture (45 minutes) – Classifier Training and Feature Identification
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour): Jupyter notebook: Edit and run existing code to:
 - Train the best performing classifier
 - Identify important features (genes) and their weights/coefficients for downstream analysis
- Quiz (15 minutes): Given output of a trained classifier, identify important features.

Module 4: Functional Analysis (part 1)

- Learning Objectives:
 1. Understand mathematical basis of GSEA[54]
 2. Know various GSEA implementations and how to use them (Broad Institute, CPA[57]...)
 3. Know various gene set ontologies (GO, KEGG, Reactome...)
- Lecture (45 minutes) – GSEA and Gene Sets
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour)
 - In a browser: use multiple GSEA implementations for functional analysis of important genes, compare outputs

- Quiz (15 minutes): No quiz, discuss scientific interpretation of trained model outputs.

Module 5: Functional Analysis (part 2)

- Learning Objectives:
 1. Be able to use open knowledge graph databases to relate rodent results to human clinical manifestations and countermeasures (spoke.ucsf.edu, time permitting; crossbar.kansil.org)
 2. Develop a hypothesis and propose future experiments to validate
- Lecture (45 minutes) – Knowledge Graphs and Hypothesis Generation
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour)
 - In a browser:
 - Input the identified features into SPOKE and time permitting, CROssBAR, to find relationships with clinical manifestations and countermeasures.
 - If time permits, compare outputs from each knowledge graph.
 - Develop a hypothesis to explain observations. Propose future biological experiments.
- Quiz (15 minutes): No quiz, discuss scientific interpretation of trained model outputs.

Topic 4: Using Neural Networks to Find DNA Damage Patterns in Immune Cells after Radiation

This Topic will focus on a real scientific use case using the BPS Microscopy cloud-based benchmark training dataset. This dataset contains thousands of fluorescent microscopy images of irradiated mouse immune cell nuclei, which have fluorescent foci indicating positivity for 53BP1, a marker of DNA damage. Cells were exposed to either ^{56}Fe or X-rays to study the effect of simulated space radiation on immune cells[58].

During spaceflight, astronauts are exposed to galactic cosmic rays (GCRs) which include heavy ions such as ^{56}Fe . These heavy ions tear through DNA double-stranded helix, causing DNA damage that is often repaired by the cell, but if not repaired can cause cancer and other illnesses[40].

This dataset is valuable for studying the patterns, incidence, and differences in DNA damage between ^{56}Fe exposure, and the X-ray control. Understanding these differences will advance our knowledge of DNA damage following space radiation exposure.

The labels published with this dataset are the radiation type and the number of 53BP1+ DNA damage foci (nfoci) per nucleus. The nfoci metric is important for assessing how damaged the cell was following radiation exposure. There is additional metadata including the radiation dose (0.3 or 0.82 Gy for ^{56}Fe , and 0.1 Gy or 1 Gy for X-ray) and the time after exposure that the image was taken (4, 24 or 48 hours). Since DNA damage is repaired by the cell over time, assessing changes in DNA damage over time in different doses and radiation types will give a better understanding of how well or poorly DNA damage is repaired in different settings.

Our use case for this study will include performing an EDA, training a convolutional neural network (CNN) to classify radiation type, implementing an xAI method to identify features of the images most important for training the classifier, and proposing biological interpretations for these features. Students will be encouraged to discuss and engage with additional ideas for analyzing this dataset outside of this course.

Students will be expected to have basic, but not advanced understanding of Python and AI/ML (taking Topic 1 first is recommended).

Below we summarize the proposed 5 modules within Topic 4.

Module 1: EDA

- Learning Objectives:
 1. How to perform an EDA on a large imagery dataset prior to AI/ML model training
- Lecture (45 minutes) – Best Practices for EDA for Image Data
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour): Jupyter notebook: Edit and run existing code to:

- Use cloud tools to download the BPS Microscopy benchmark training dataset
- Perform an EDA
- Quiz (15 minutes): Given outputs of a hypothetical EDA, identify any interesting or concerning results.

Module 2: Training CNN (part 1)

- Learning Objectives:
 1. How to train a CNN on a large imagery dataset
 2. How to implement grid search for optimal hyperparameters
- Lecture (45 minutes) – CNN and Grid Search
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour): Jupyter notebook: Edit and run existing code to:
 - Start training a CNN to classify radiation type (Fe or X-ray)
 - Grid search on small data set to identify optimal hyperparameters
- Quiz (15 minutes): Describe CNN capabilities and limitations.

Module 3: Training CNN (part 2)

- Learning Objectives:
 1. How to train a CNN on a large imagery dataset
 2. Validate performance of a CNN
- Lecture (45 minutes) – CNN and Performance Validation
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour): Jupyter notebook: Edit and run existing code to:
 - Finish training the CNN model and report model performance
- Quiz (15 minutes): Describe how to validate the performance of a CNN.

Module 4: xAI

- Learning Objectives:
 1. How to implement GradCam, an xAI method for images
- Lecture (45 minutes) – xAI for Biological Imagery
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour): Jupyter notebook: Edit and run existing code to:
 - Implement GradCam
 - Identify the features used by the CNN for classification
- Quiz (15 minutes): No quiz, discuss scientific interpretation of trained model outputs.

Module 5: Biological Interpretations

- Learning Objectives:
 1. How to interpret xAI of microscopy data in the context of space biology
- Lecture (45 minutes) – Space Biology Microscopy Background
- Guided Hands-on Activity (1.5 hour): Discussion:
 - Interpret the xAI features of the microscopy images in the context of space biology, develop a biological model and hypothesis to explain observations, and propose future biological experiments.
- Quiz (15 minutes): No quiz, discuss scientific interpretation of trained model outputs.

Timeline

Quarter	Activities (Responsible parties in italics)	Deliverables
Q1	-Develop lecture materials for Topic 1 (<i>PI, Co-I #2</i>) -Develop lecture materials for Topic 2 (<i>PI, Co-I #2, Co-I #3</i>) -Review and finalize Topic 1 and Topic 2 lectures (<i>all</i>) -Record Topic 1 and Topic 2 lectures (<i>PI, Co-I #2</i>) -Develop and test Jupyter notebooks for Topic 1 (<i>PI, Co-I #2</i>)	-Slide decks and recorded lectures for Topics 1 and 2

2023	Q2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Review and finalize Jupyter notebooks for Topic 1 (<i>all</i>) -Develop and test Jupyter notebooks for Topic 2 (<i>PI, Co-I #2</i>) -Review and finalize Jupyter notebooks for Topic 2 (<i>all</i>) -Develop the Case Study Discussions for Topic 2 and design handouts/case study discussion aids(<i>all</i>) -Develop lecture materials for Topic 3 (<i>PI, Co-I #2</i>) -Review and finalize Topic 3 lectures (<i>all</i>) -Record Topic 3 lectures (<i>PI, Co-I #2</i>) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Jupyter Notebooks for Topics 1 and 2 -Case Study Discussions for Topic 2 - Slide decks and recorded lectures for Topic 3
	Q3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Develop and test Jupyter notebooks for Topic 3 (<i>PI, Co-I #2</i>) -Review and finalize Jupyter notebooks for Topic 3 (<i>all</i>) -Develop handouts for the browser-based hands-on activities for Topic 3 (<i>PI, Co-I #2</i>) -Review and finalize Topic 3 hands-on handouts (<i>all</i>) -Develop lecture materials for Topic 4 -Review and finalize Topic 4 lecture materials (<i>all</i>) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Jupyter notebooks for Topic 3 -Hands-on guided activities handouts for Topic 3 -Slides for Topic 4 lectures
	Q4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Record Topic 4 lectures (<i>PI, Co-I #2</i>) -Develop and test Jupyter notebooks for Topic 4 (<i>PI, Co-I #2</i>) -Review and finalize Jupyter notebooks for Topic 4 (<i>all</i>) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Recorded lectures for Topic 4 -Jupyter notebooks for Topic 4

Accessibility and Openness

In keeping with Open Science core values, we implement the following measures to ensure accessibility and openness. The proposed training materials will be built openly on GitHub, allowing public access and contributions from anyone interested in doing so. Lectures will be recorded and hosted on YouTube, ensuring transcription services and accessibility to those with auditory needs. Each of our modules is designed to contain narrative and executable interactive content. Finally, one of our Co-Is is fluent in French and will create French versions of all curricula. This will enable ease of accessibility for students from French-speaking areas, including France, Canada, and many countries in Africa.

Limitations, Pitfalls, and Possible Adjustments

Model Training

For Topics 1, 3 and 4, we propose to develop training materials that involve training an AI/ML model on real biological data. It will be preferable for the students to actually train the model in real-time, but this may not be possible in all training situations (given limited time or limited compute power). Therefore, in parallel to the main training materials, we will provide pre-trained versions of all Jupyter Notebooks that involve training a model. In the pre-trained curriculum versions, we will provide pre-trained models and accompanying code to guide the students to load each model into a Jupyter Notebook and train for a few more epochs to assess the final performance of the model. We will publish full training metrics for all pretrained models and include these in the pre-trained curriculum versions, so that the students can review and discuss the training metrics if they do not train the models themselves in real-time.

Time for Lectures and Hands-on Activities

In developing and testing these materials, we may find that some modules are too complex and lengthy to fit into one 2.5 hour training day. In this case, we will re-evaluate the content and will likely split the content of that Topic into multiple 5-module weeks.

REFERENCES

1. Jordan MI, Mitchell TM. Machine learning: Trends, perspectives, and prospects. *Science*. 2015;349: 255–260.
2. AlQuraishi M, Sorger PK. Differentiable biology: using deep learning for biophysics-based and data-driven modeling of molecular mechanisms. *Nat Methods*. 2021;18: 1169–1180.
3. Topol EJ. High-performance medicine: the convergence of human and artificial intelligence. *Nat Med*. 2019;25: 44–56.
4. Xu C, Jackson SA. Machine learning and complex biological data. *Genome Biol*. 2019;20: 76.
5. AlQuraishi M. AlphaFold at CASP13. *Bioinformatics*. 2019;35: 4862–4865.
6. Zieliński B, Plichta A, Misztal K, Spurek P, Brzywczy-Włoch M, Ochońska D. Deep learning approach to bacterial colony classification. *PLoS One*. 2017;12: e0184554.
7. Nelson CA, Bove R, Butte AJ, Baranzini SE. Embedding electronic health records onto a knowledge network recognizes prodromal features of multiple sclerosis and predicts diagnosis. *J Am Med Inform Assoc*. 2021. doi:10.1093/jamia/ocab270
8. Fu L, Li Y, Cheng A, Pang P, Shu Z. A novel machine learning-derived radiomic signature of the whole lung differentiates stable from progressive COVID-19 infection: A retrospective cohort study. *J Thorac Imaging*. 2020;35: 361–368.
9. Gunčar G, Kukar M, Notar M, Brvar M, Černelč P, Notar M, et al. An application of machine learning to haematological diagnosis. *Sci Rep*. 2018;8: 411.
10. Bashiri A, Ghazisaeedi M, Safdari R, Shahmoradi L, Ehtesham H. Improving the prediction of survival in cancer patients by using machine learning techniques: Experience of gene expression data: A narrative review. *Iran J Public Health*. 2017;46: 165–172.
11. Menden MP, Iorio F, Garnett M, McDermott U, Benes CH, Ballester PJ, et al. Machine learning prediction of cancer cell sensitivity to drugs based on genomic and chemical properties. *PLoS One*. 2013;8: e61318.
12. SkyQuest Technology Consulting Pvt. Ltd. Global Computational Biology Market to Touch \$14.7 Billion by 2028. 13 Sep 2022 [cited 25 Nov 2022]. Available: <https://www.globenewswire.com/en/news-release/2022/09/13/2515299/0/en/Global-Computational-Biology-Market-to-Touch-14-7-Billion-by-2028-Preclinical-Drug-Discovery-is-Offering-Lucrative-Opportunity.html>
13. National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, Policy and Global Affairs, Board on Research Data and Information, Committee on Toward an Open Science Enterprise. *Open Science by Design: Realizing a Vision for 21st Century Research*. Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US); 2018.
14. Wynants L, Van Calster B, Collins GS, Riley RD, Heinze G, Schuit E, et al. Prediction models for diagnosis and prognosis of covid-19: systematic review and critical appraisal. *BMJ*. 2020;369: m1328.
15. Strategic Data Management Working Group. *Strategy for Data Management and Computing for Groundbreaking Science 2019-2024*. NASA Science Mission Directorate. 2019. Available: https://science.nasa.gov/science-pink/s3fs-public/atoms/files/SDMWG%20Strategy_Final.pdf
16. Nelson CA, Acuna AU, Paul AM, Scott RT, Butte AJ, Cekanaviciute E, et al. Knowledge Network Embedding of Transcriptomic Data from Spaceflown Mice Uncovers Signs and Symptoms Associated with Terrestrial Diseases. *Life*. 2021;11. doi:10.3390/life11010042
17. Budd S, Blaas A, Hoarfrost A, Khezeli K, D'Silva K, Soboczenski F, et al. Prototyping CRISP: A Causal Relation and Inference Search Platform applied to Colorectal Cancer Data. 2021 IEEE 3rd Global Conference on Life Sciences and Technologies

(LifeTech). ieeexplore.ieee.org; 2021. pp. 517–521.

18. Duckworth P, O'Donoghue O, Scheibenreif L, Ughi G, Hoarfrost A, Budd S, et al. Federated causal inference for out-of-distribution generalization in predicting physiological effects of radiation exposure. Frontier Development Lab Technical Memorandum; 2021 Aug. Available: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1xM8USgeYs-NNbB83JSUI4EnfMG09W1Se/view>
19. Matar M, Gokoglu SA, Prelich MT, Gallo CA, Iqbal AK, Britten RA, et al. Machine Learning Models to Predict Cognitive Impairment of Rodents Subjected to Space Radiation. *Front Syst Neurosci.* 2021;15: 713131.
20. Prelich MT, Matar M, Gokoglu SA, Gallo CA, Schepelmann A, Iqbal AK, et al. Predicting Space Radiation Single Ion Exposure in Rodents: A Machine Learning Approach. *Front Syst Neurosci.* 2021;15: 111.
21. Vyas RJ, Young M, Murray MC, Predovic M, Lim S, Jacobs NM, et al. Decreased Vascular Patterning in the Retinas of Astronaut Crew Members as New Measure of Ocular Damage in Spaceflight-Associated Neuro-ocular Syndrome. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci.* 2020;61: 34.
22. Parsons-Wingerter P, Reinecker H-C. For Application to Human Spaceflight and ISS Experiments: VESGEN Mapping of Microvascular Network Remodeling during Intestinal Inflammation. *Gravit Space Biol Bull.* 2012;26: 2–12.
23. Parsons-Wingerter P, Hosamani R, Vickerman MB, Bhattacharya S. Mapping by VESGEN of Wing Vein Phenotype in for Quantifying Adaptations to Space Environments. *Gravitational and Space Research.* 2015;3: 54–64.
24. Madrigal P, Singh NK, Wood JM, Gaudio E, Hernández-Del-Olmo F, Mason CE, et al. Machine learning algorithm to characterize antimicrobial resistance associated with the International Space Station surface microbiome. *Microbiome.* 2022;10: 134.
25. Scott RT, Antonsen EL, Sanders LM, Hastings JJA, Park S-M, Mackintosh G, et al. Beyond Low Earth Orbit: Biomonitoring, Artificial Intelligence, and Precision Space Health. *arXiv.* 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2112.12554>
26. Sanders LM, Yang JH, Scott RT, Qutub AA, Martin HG, Berrios DC, et al. Beyond Low Earth Orbit: Biological Research, Artificial Intelligence, and Self-Driving Labs. *arXiv.* 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2112.12582>
27. Theriot CA. TOPICAL: Enabling a Precision Health System for Deep Space Exploration. *Life and Physical Sciences 2023-2032 Decadal Topical.* 2021. Available: http://surveygizmoreponseuploads.s3.amazonaws.com/fileuploads/623127/6378869/194-1d135908586055690fce80bab429eb99_TheriotCoreyA.pdf
28. Sanders LM, Scott RT, Costes SV. Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence and Data Modeling for the Next Decade of Space Biology Research and Astronaut Health Support. A White Paper Submitted on 23 December 2021, to the Committee on Biological and Physical Sciences in Space for the 2023-2032 Decadal Survey. 2021. Available: http://surveygizmoreponseuploads.s3.amazonaws.com/fileuploads/623127/6392490/153-d4da81bc2b0f81447a9adb0dcb878e64_SandersLaurenM.pdf
29. Clark KB. Topical: Intelligent Meta-Learning Inferential Social Robotic and Virtual Space-Medicine Clinicians. A White Paper Submitted on 23 December 2021 to the Committee on Biological and Physical Sciences in Space for the 2023-2032 Decadal Survey; 2021 Dec. Available: http://surveygizmoreponseuploads.s3.amazonaws.com/fileuploads%2F623127%2F6378869%2F156-d6508408d6ebfec463313444184ad45b_ClarkKevinB3.1.pdf
30. Tabetah M. Research Campaign: Automation and Artificial Intelligence for Materials Research in Low Earth Orbit. A White Paper Submitted on 23 December 2021 to the Committee on Biological and Physical Sciences in Space for the 2023-2032 Decadal Survey; 2021 Dec. Available:

http://surveygizmoreponseuploads.s3.amazonaws.com/fileuploads%2F623127%2F6392490%2F27-b703e5514d99eea6651676a1a6c2ee77_TabetahMarshallE.docx

31. Sanders LM. Topical: Development of new algorithms for space biology. Life and Physical Sciences 2023-2032 Decadal Topical. 2021. Available:

http://surveygizmoreponseuploads.s3.amazonaws.com/fileuploads/623127/6378869/217-4826dc0ada8fb5a9ec7d5a1167b9523b_SandersLaurenM.pdf

32. Larkin E, Schuerger A, Barker R, Lee JA, Haveman N, Enciso JF, et al. GROUND AND FLIGHT-BASED PLANT MICROBIAL INTERACTION RESEARCH AND RELATED SPACE CROP PRODUCTION APPLICATIONS. A White Paper Submitted on 23 December 2021, to the Committee on Biological and Physical Sciences in Space for the 2023-2032 Decadal Survey. 2021. Available:

<https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20210023782/downloads/LarkinEmerickM.pdf>

33. Tabetah M. Topical: Gaining Insights from Omics Data Using Artificial Intelligence in Space Crop Production. A White Paper Submitted on 23 December 2021 to the Committee on Biological and Physical Sciences in Space for the 2023-2032 Decadal Survey; 2021 Dec. Available:

http://surveygizmoreponseuploads.s3.amazonaws.com/fileuploads%2F623127%2F6378869%2F85-c13659d102e301fc2c763419f3be792d_TabetahMarshallE.docx

34. Escobar C, Altaf N, Barker R, Bhuiyan M, Correll M, Fritsche R, et al. Research campaign - artificial intelligence for autonomous space plant production. A White Paper Submitted on 23 December 2021 to the Committee on Biological and Physical Sciences in Space for the 2023-2032 Decadal Survey; Available:

http://surveygizmoreponseuploads.s3.amazonaws.com/fileuploads%2F623127%2F6392490%2F47-7b34a38f75ed824552f1e41774330422_EscobarChristineM.pdf

35. Shevtsov J, Escobar C, Schuerger AC, Trouillefou CM, Tuominen LK, Wheeler R. Research Campaign: Bioregenerative life support systems: Coordinated research into organisms, technology and systems integration. A White Paper Submitted on 23 December 2021 to the Committee on Biological and Physical Sciences in Space for the 2023-2032 Decadal Survey; 2021 Dec. Available:

http://surveygizmoreponseuploads.s3.amazonaws.com/fileuploads%2F623127%2F6392490%2F238-6ff87ea936983a40220107cf200cb6b8_ShevtsovJane.pdf

36. Berrios DC, Galazka J, Grigorev K, Gebre S, Costes SV. NASA GeneLab: interfaces for the exploration of space omics data. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2021;49: D1515–D1522.

37. Ray S, Gebre S, Fogle H, Berrios DC, Tran PB, Galazka JM, et al. GeneLab: Omics database for spaceflight experiments. *Bioinformatics.* 2019;35: 1753–1759.

38. Scott RT, Grigorev K, Mackintosh G, Gebre SG, Mason CE, Del Alto ME, et al. Advancing the Integration of Biosciences Data Sharing to Further Enable Space Exploration. *Cell Rep.* 2020;33: 108441.

39. Bzdok D, Altman N, Krzywinski M. Statistics versus machine learning. *Nat Methods.* 2018;15: 233–234.

40. Afshinnekoo E, Scott RT, MacKay MJ, Pariset E, Cekanaviciute E, Barker R, et al. Fundamental Biological Features of Spaceflight: Advancing the Field to Enable Deep-Space Exploration. *Cell.* 2020;183: 1162–1184.

41. Ribeiro MT, Singh S, Guestrin C. “Why Should I Trust You?”: Explaining the Predictions of Any Classifier. *arXiv [cs.LG]*. 2016. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1602.04938>

42. Schmidhuber J. Deep learning in neural networks: an overview. *Neural Netw.* 2015;61: 85–117.

43. O’Donoghue O, Duckworth P, Ughi G, Scheibenreif L, Khezeli K, Hoarfrost A, et al. Invariant Risk Minimisation for Cross-Organism Inference: Substituting Mouse Data for Human Data in Human Risk Factor Discovery. *arXiv [cs.LG]*. 2021. Available:

<http://arxiv.org/abs/2111.07348>

44. Boenig-Liptsin M, Tanweer A, Edmundson A. Data Science Ethos Lifecycle: Interplay of Ethical Thinking and Data Science Practice. *Journal of Statistics and Data Science Education*. 2022;30: 228–240.
45. Adadi A, Berrada M. Explainable AI for Healthcare: From Black Box to Interpretable Models. *Embedded Systems and Artificial Intelligence*. Springer Singapore; 2020. pp. 327–337.
46. Stall S, Yarmey L, Cutcher-Gershenfeld J, Hanson B, Lehnert K, Nosek B, et al. Make scientific data FAIR. *Nature*. 2019;570: 27–29.
47. Haibe-Kains B, Adam GA, Hosny A, Khodakarami F, Massive Analysis Quality Control (MAQC) Society Board of Directors, Waldron L, et al. Transparency and reproducibility in artificial intelligence. *Nature*. 2020. pp. E14–E16.
48. Hutson M. Artificial intelligence faces reproducibility crisis. *Science*. 2018;359: 725–726.
49. Baker M. Reproducibility crisis. *Nature*. 2016;533: 353–366.
50. Mark S, Scott GBI, Donoviel DB, Leveton LB, Mahoney E, Charles JB, et al. The impact of sex and gender on adaptation to space: executive summary. *J Womens Health* . 2014;23: 941–947.
51. Jonscher KR, Alfonso-Garcia A, Suhaimi JL, Orlicky DJ, Potma EO, Ferguson VL, et al. Spaceflight Activates Lipotoxic Pathways in Mouse Liver. *PLoS One*. 2016;11: e0152877.
52. Beheshti A, Chakravarty K, Fogle H, Fazelinia H, Silveira WA da, Boyko V, et al. Multi-omics analysis of multiple missions to space reveal a theme of lipid dysregulation in mouse liver. *Sci Rep*. 2019;9: 19195.
53. Garrett-Bakelman FE, Darshi M, Green SJ, Gur RC, Lin L, Macias BR, et al. The NASA Twins Study: A multidimensional analysis of a year-long human spaceflight. *Science*. 2019;364. doi:10.1126/science.aau8650
54. Subramanian A, Tamayo P, Mootha VK, Mukherjee S, Ebert BL, Gillette MA, et al. Gene set enrichment analysis: a knowledge-based approach for interpreting genome-wide expression profiles. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2005;102: 15545–15550.
55. Nelson CA, Butte AJ, Baranzini SE. Integrating biomedical research and electronic health records to create knowledge-based biologically meaningful machine-readable embeddings. *Nat Commun*. 2019;10: 3045.
56. Doğan T, Atas H, Joshi V, Atakan A, Rifaioglu AS, Nalbat E, et al. CROssBAR: comprehensive resource of biomedical relations with knowledge graph representations. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2021;49: e96.
57. Nguyen H, Tran D, Galazka JM, Costes SV, Beheshti A, Petereit J, et al. CPA: a web-based platform for consensus pathway analysis and interactive visualization. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2021;49: W114–W124.
58. Penninckx S, Cekanaviciute E, Degorre C, Guiet E, Viger L, Lucas S, et al. Dose, LET and Strain Dependence of Radiation-Induced 53BP1 Foci in 15 Mouse Strains Ex Vivo Introducing Novel DNA Damage Metrics. *Radiat Res*. 2019;192: 1–12.

OPEN-SOURCE SCIENCE DEVELOPMENT PLAN

All lecture materials, handouts, and Jupyter notebooks will be made publicly available via GitHub, with the ability for the scientific community to provide feedback and contributions. Lectures will be recorded and hosted publicly on YouTube.

SUMMARY TABLE OF WORK EFFORT (ANONYMIZED)

Role	Effort
PI	30%
Co-I #1	5%
Co-I #2	50%
Co-I #3	5%

REDACTED BUDGET AND NARRATIVE

Key Personnel

PI. Effort = 12 calendar months, 30% FY23. The PI will oversee all scientific and curriculum development aspects of this project, including but not limited to: lecture materials, quizzes, recorded videos; recruiting and supervising personnel; compliance with timeline, budget, and deliverables; and leading the preparation of conference presentations.

Co-I #1. FTE = 0.05 FY23. Co-I #1 will provide oversight and expertise for curriculum development, data analysis and algorithm design for training materials.

Co-I #2. Effort = 12 calendar months, 50% FY23. Co-I #2 will be responsible for the majority of the hands-on curriculum development. Co-I #2 will be responsible for translating all training materials into French. Co-I #2 will work with the PI to make decisions about the design of lecture materials, quizzes, videos, and data analysis training. Co-I #2 will put together the training materials and deliverables together with the PI, and will participate in conference presentations.

Co-I #3. Effort = 12 calendar months, 5% FY23. Co-I #3 will provide oversight and expertise for curriculum development, data analysis and conference presentations.

The total cost for personnel is included in the separately uploaded Total Budget PDF file but is not included here in the proposal.

Travel

Conferences. Funds are allocated for the PI or Co-PI #2 to attend the annual 4-day TOPS coordination meeting in Washington DC in FY23, and one other conference to present this work. Based on prior travel costs combining airfare, hotel and meal expenses, we estimate \$2,500 per trip, \$5,000.

Total for travel: \$5,000

Compute

We estimate that developing and testing the AI/ML model training portions of the curricula will require 10 months on a 1-GPU notebook server. Based on prior compute costs, we estimate \$500 per month, \$5,000.

Total for compute: \$5,000